

SMART FARMING: LEVERAGING IOT AND ML FOR OPTIMIZED CROP SELECTION

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ABSTRACT-- Agriculture plays a vital role in maintaining environmental balance. Sustainable farming practices help preserve soil fertility, conserve water resources, and protect biodiversity. The conventional methods often rely on historical data and are instinctive for crop selection, hence it tends to suboptimal outcomes and inefficiencies. Farmers are able to make data-driven decisions about crop selection because to the combination of IoT and ML, which increases yields, decreases resource waste, and improves sustainability. Furthermore, by continuously collecting and analyzing data, the system can adapt to changing environmental conditions, further optimizing crop selection over time. This paper discusses the key components of a smart farming system, including data collection through IoT devices, data processing using ML algorithms, and decision-making processes for suitable crop selection. This paper presents a variety of techniques such as Random Forest, KNN, and Naive Bayes. The proposed system aims to optimize crop selection and management processes by leveraging real-time environmental data congregated through IoT sensors. The predicted results will be displayed in the IOT platform. By harnessing IoT devices such as sensors, farmers can collect real-time data on different types of environmental factors, including soil moisture, temperature, humidity, and crop health. This data act as foundation for informed decision-making system. This system contributes to the advancement of smart agriculture technologies, offering a scalable and intelligent solution to deal with the issues that contemporary agricultural systems confront.

KEYWORDS-- Internet of Things, Machine Learning, Algorithm, KNN, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Sensors, ThingSpeak.

I. INTRODUCTION

The agriculture industry is at a turning point in a time of increasing global issues including population increase, point in a time of increasing global issues including resource scarcity, population increase, and climate change.

Traditional approaches to crop selection often rely on historical data, anecdotal evidence, and expert intuition. However, these methods are increasingly inadequate in the face of escalating climate variability, resource constraints, and evolving market demands. Traditional farming point in a time of increasing global issues including practices are no longer sufficient to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world. The advent of Smart Farming signifies a dramatic change in this regard. Precision agriculture, often known as smart farming, is the fusion of modern technology with traditional agricultural methods. Smart farming gives farmers access to previously unheard- levels of insight, control, and efficiency by fusing a wide range of technologies, Machine learning (ML), and the Internet of Things (IoT). In this context, the emergence of Smart Farming represents a revolutionary shift. Thus it represents the convergence of cutting-edge technologies with age-old agricultural practices. At its core, Smart Farming harnesses the power of digital innovation to optimize every facet of the farming process, from planting and irrigation to harvesting and distribution. By integrating a diverse array of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and data analytics, Smart Farming empowers farmers with unprecedented insights, control, and efficiency. Smart Farming, by contrast, offers a dynamic and responsive framework that leverages real-time data from IoT sensors deployed across agricultural landscapes. Through the deployment of IoT sensors and connected devices across agricultural landscapes, farmers gain real-time visibility into crucial variables such as soil wetness levels, Meteorology conditions, crop robustness indicators, and machinery performance.

II. RELATED WORKS

[1] The SVM, Random forest, and ID3 algorithms are used to examine a machine learning framework for agricultural yield prediction.

[2] This system monitors the farmland remotely by farmers and uses various sensors to collect the data. This system's second goal is to provide a system prototype for an animal incursion detection system. A local personal computer plays

a camera that records the live-streaming footage. The video's frames are taken out and converted to photos. The image is fed to machine learning techniques. The model analyses whether the wild animal is near or far the field. It notifies the farmer by the app notification.

[3] This paper gives a literature review of the existing crop recommendation systems. In the future, a web/mobile application with a user-friendly interface is preferred with factors such as the economic status of farmers, fertilizer requirements, topography, soil nutrients, and properties.

[4] This system uses a machine learning linear regression algorithm to recommend crops. It uses datasets from the government website and Kaggle. It analyses and processes the datasets for crop recommendation. It predicts crop sustainability from the fed datasets.

[5] The farmers use a fuzzy-based rough set strategy to assist them in choosing the crops for their fields. Twenty-four distinct crops were used in the testing of this method, and the primary criteria for 16 input qualities were Potential of hydrogen, soil type, and location. In the future, an android application that tracks suitable crop recommendations, soil robustness, and type will be created.

Thus Precision farming is about to take off as a result of the merging of IoT and machine learning, which is bringing about a paradigm shift in agricultural techniques. Farmers may increase productivity, reduce resource consumption, and help ensure a more sustainable future for agriculture by utilizing data-driven insights. The aim of this paper is to study the possibilities of this novel strategy and how it might affect and be useful to the agriculture industry.

III. METHODOLOGY

The NodeMCU collects the data from the sensors, processes the data, and communicates with other components of the system, such as the cloud or a local server. The main power supply is 12 volts since the sensors and the system operate at 5 volts so, we use a Buck converter to convert the voltage to 5 volts. The DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor and pH sensor are directly connected to the microcontroller since they are digital sensors. The MQ135 air quality sensor and moisture sensor are analog sensors; hence, the MCP3008 Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC), which is 10-bit, is used for the conversion of the analog values to digital data. Based on the ESP8266 microprocessor, the NodeMCU is an open-source development board. Because of its integrated Wi-Fi capabilities, it's perfect for Internet of Things applications. The temperature and humidity of the surrounding air, which are critical elements for crop growth, will be measured by the DHT11 sensor and reported. The soil's acidity, or

alkalinity, will be measured by the pH sensor, which is an essential tool for figuring out whether the soil is suitable for a given crop. Ammonia, benzene, and smoke are just a few of the air quality factors that the MQ135 sensor can measure. Crop health may be impacted by the general air quality, which can be evaluated using this data. The soil's moisture content will be measured by the moisture sensor.

The Microcontroller NodeMCU, equipped with sensors, collects environmental data like soil moisture, temperature, and humidity. It then transmits this data to ThingSpeak, a cloud-based IoT platform, via Wi-Fi connectivity.

ThingSpeak stores the incoming sensor data in its cloud storage. This historical data forms the basis for training and refining machine learning models for crop recommendation. This may include data cleaning, normalization, and feature extraction to prepare the data for the model training.

Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Naïve Bayes algorithms are trained using the pre-processed sensor data stored in ThingSpeak. Cloud-based computational resources enable efficient training of complex models. Once trained, the machine learning models are deployed on the cloud platform. When new sensor data arrives, the deployed models make real-time predictions for crop recommendations based on the current environmental conditions. ThingSpeak provides visualization tools such as tables, and charts to display the results of the crop recommendation system. These visualizations can be embedded in web pages or accessed via ThingSpeak's API, allowing users to monitor recommendations remotely.

A) Proposed ML Models

The proposed system involves the classification of crops based on environmental factors and suggesting a crop based on the parameters obtained from the field. The environmental factors that affect the growth of crops include pH, temperature, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, humidity, and soil moisture. The dataset contains data for 13 different crops, such as Banana, Black gram, Carrot, Cauliflower, Corn, Cotton, Green chili, Green gram, Onion, Rice, Sugarcane, Tomato, and wheat. There are a total of 50086 instances in the dataset. The dataset is fed to the system, a machine learning model, and it learns to make predictions for the tasks that are given. The machine learning models chosen for the analysis of crop recommendations are described below.

1. KNN

The supervised learning method is the foundation of K-Nearest Neighbor, one of the most fundamental machine learning algorithms. Based on the assumption that the new

instance and its data are similar to the examples that are already available, the KNN approach assigns the new case to the category that is most equivalent to the existing categories. Once all relevant information has been stored, a new data point is classified using the KNN algorithm based on similarity. This suggests that freshly found data can be swiftly categorized into the most appropriate category using the KNN method.

2. RANDOM FOREST

One popular machine learning algorithm is Random Forest, which is used in supervised learning techniques. It can be used for machine learning problems that involve classification and regression. Its basis is the concept of ensemble learning, which is the act of combining multiple classifiers to improve the functionality of the model and solve a difficult problem. A classifier called Random Forest uses many decision trees on different dataset subsets and averages them to increase the dataset's predicted accuracy. Instead of depending just on one decision tree, the random forest makes forecasts based on the majority choice of predictions for each one.

3. NAÏVE BAYES

Supervised learning is the foundation of the Naïve Bayes method. It is mainly used for classification-related models, and it is developed using the Bayes theorem. Instead of being a single algorithm, it is a group of algorithms built around the same concept. One of the most uncomplicated as well as effective for classification, the Naïve Bayes classifier facilitates the speedy development of machine learning models with accurate prediction capabilities. Making predictions by considering the event that an object occurs, and so it is called a probabilistic classifier.

B) Block Diagram

Fig. 1. Block diagram of Optimized crop selection system

NodeMCU gathers data from sensors that measure parameters like humidity, temperature, and soil moisture. Utilizing Random Forest, Naive Bayes, and KNN algorithms, data is processed to recommend suitable crops; outcomes are compared on Thingspeak for optimal crop selection.

C) Flow Chart

Fig. 2. Flow Chart of the algorithm implementation

The optimized crop selection system uses Machine Learning algorithms and IoT and collects environmental data like soil moisture, temperature, humidity, and air quality using sensors connected to the NodeMCU. Using Random Forest, KNN, and Naive Bayes algorithms, machine learning models are constructed to evaluate gathered data and recommend suitable crops according to the predefined criteria. The models are trained using historical agricultural data to enhance accuracy. The performance of these algorithms is compared to determine the most effective one to predict suitable crops for precise farming. For processing, this data is sent to a server or cloud service. The predicted results is displayed along with real-time sensor data on the ThingSpeak web page, enabling users to access predictions and monitor environmental conditions remotely.

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Temperature, humidity, pH, and a variety of crops are among the features included in the training dataset that was used to train the crop prediction model. This work presents three distinct techniques: KNN, Random Forest, and Naive Bayes. Random forest has exhibited superior accuracy compared to other machine learning algorithms. Agricultural datasets frequently contain noise and outliers, yet random forests are resistant to these types of events. They also provide an improved way to deal with missing data. A node's most frequently occurring variable replaces

any missing values. The random forest method is also capable of managing large amounts of data with several thousand variables. When a class appears less frequently in the data than other classes, it can automatically balance data sets. By ignoring the inaccurate data, the projections' accuracy is improved with the help of the farmer's feedback.

A) Algorithm Comparison:

ALGORITHM	ACCURACY
Random Forest	1
KNN	0.99
Naive Bayes	0.23

Table I. Comparison of Accuracy of Algorithms

Fig. 3. Accuracy graph for different algorithms

The above Fig. 3. represents the outcomes of algorithms in the suggested study among which Random forest demonstrated high accuracy.

B) Performance Metrics

Performance metrics are greatly helpful in assessing the system's effectiveness and also help in obtaining valuable insights from the model. They are explained below. Precision is all about evaluating the positive predictions of the model and analysing how accurate these predictions are. Recall evaluates how effectively the model detects the relevant instances within a dataset. Being a performance metric, the F1 score combines recall and precision scores to evaluate the model. By utilizing the harmonic mean of the two metrics, F1 score aggregates the two, thus optimizing

the F1 score. Accuracy evaluates how frequently the model forecasts the correct outcome. It is the total correct outcomes divided by the total outcomes. A confusion matrix helps in obtaining insights about how well the model performs on a set of test data. It is a way to show the number of correct and incorrect instances in the model's prediction.

ALGORITHM	PRECISION	RECALL	F1	ACCURACY
Random Forest	1	1	1	1
KNN	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99
Naive Bayes	0.24	0.24	0.23	0.23

Table II. Performance metrics comparison for different algorithms

Fig. 4. Comparison graph of performance metrics of algorithms

The above Fig. 4. shows the comparison of each performance metrics of algorithms in the suggested study.

C) Crop Prediction by Random Forest Algorithm

CROPS	PRECISION	RECALL	F1
BANANA	1	1	1
BLACK GRAM	0.99	1	1
CARROT	1	1	1
CAULIFLOWER	1	1	1
CORN	1	1	1
COTTON	1	1	1

GREEN CHILLI	1	1	1
GREEN GRAM	1	0.99	0.99
ONION	1	1	1
RICE	1	1	1
SUGARCANE	1	1	1
TOMATO	1	1	1
WHEAT	1	1	1

Table III. Performance metrics of Random forest algorithm

CORN	0.98	0.99	0.99
COTTON	0.98	0.99	0.99
GREEN CHILLI	1	1	1
GREEN GRAM	0.99	0.99	0.99
ONION	1	1	1
RICE	0.99	0.98	0.99
SUGARCANE	0.99	0.98	0.99
TOMATO	1	1	1
WHEAT	1	0.97	0.99

Table IV. Performance metrics of KNN algorithm

Fig. 5. Performance metrics of Random forest algorithm

Fig. 6. Performance metrics of KNN algorithm

The above Fig. 5. represents the performance metrics of the Random forest algorithm for each crop in the model.

The above Fig. 6. represents the performance metrics of KNN algorithm for each crop in the model.

D) Crop Prediction by KNN Algorithm

E) Crop Prediction by Naïve Bayes Algorithm

CROPS	PRECISION	RECALL	F1
BANANA	1	1	1
BLACK GRAM	0.96	1	0.98
CARROT	1	1	1
CAULIFLOWER	1	1	1

CROPS	PRECISION	RECALL	F1
BANANA	1	1	1
BLACK GRAM	0.15	0.18	0.16
CARROT	1	1	1
CAULIFLOWER	0	0	0

CORN	0.14	0.13	0.13
COTTON	0.17	0.05	0.08
GREEN CHILLI	0	0	0
GREEN GRAM	0.17	0.21	0.18
ONION	0	0	0
RICE	0.18	0.09	0.12
SUGARCANE	0.15	0.19	0.17
TOMATO	0	0	0
WHEAT	0.14	0.22	0.17

Table V. Performance metrics of Naïve Bayes algorithm

Fig. 7. Performance metrics of Naïve Bayes algorithm

The above Fig. 7. represents the performance metrics of the Naïve Bayes algorithm for each crop in the model.

F) Real-Time Data Display

Real-Time Data Display

Timestamp	TEMP	Humidity	PH	GAS	RESULT
27/3/2024, 12:42:59 pm	7	32	40	129	['Wheat']
27/3/2024, 12:44:10 pm	7	32	40	120	['Corn']
27/3/2024, 12:44:56 pm	7	32	40	101	['Wheat']
27/3/2024, 12:53:07 pm	7	33	36	79	['Cotton']
27/3/2024, 1:01:14 pm	7	33	36	80	['Sugarcane']

Fig. 8. Web page displaying real-time parameters

The web page displays the real-time data which can be monitored remotely.

G) Confusion Matrix of Random Forest, KNN, Naïve Bayes Algorithm

I. Random Forest

II KNN

III. Naïve Bayes

Fig. 9. Confusion matrix of I. Random Forest II. KNN III. Naïve Bayes algorithm

The above Fig. 9. displays the Confusion Matrix of Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbour, and Naïve Bayes Algorithms by Machine Learning Techniques.

By offering individualized recommendations based on information like pH, temperature, humidity, and air quality, our system presents the suggested model as a useful tool for farmers to maximize yields. After experimenting with various divisions for the training and test data, we ultimately decided on 80% training and 20% testing. Random forest outperformed KNN by 0.01, with an average score of 1.00 across all cases compared to 0.99 for KNN. Naïve Bayes produced the lowest performance among the three algorithms with a score of 0.24.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the fusion of Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning (ML) technologies in a crop recommendation system represents a significant stride toward revolutionizing agricultural practices. By leveraging the capabilities of IoT devices such as NodeMCU and sensors to collect real-time environmental data and employing ML algorithms for predictive analysis, this system offers invaluable insights to farmers for making informed decisions about crop selection.

The future scope for crop recommendation systems integrating IoT and ML holds immense potential for revolutionizing agriculture. The emerging technologies such as edge computing and blockchain can enhance data security, privacy, and interoperability while enabling real-time decision-making at the farm level. Collaborative research efforts focusing on interdisciplinary approaches, including agronomy, computer science, and data science, will be instrumental in developing holistic solutions that address the diverse needs and challenges of farmers worldwide.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Dr. Kanaga Suba Raja S, Durai Arumugam S. S. L, Dr. R. Praveenkumar, Dr. V. Balaji “ An Intelligent Crop Recommendation System using Deep Learning ” International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering (IJISAE 2023).
- [2] Shafiulla Shariff, R. B. Shwetha, O. G. Ramya, H. Pushpa, K. R. Pooja, “Crop Recommendation using Machine Learning Techniques,” International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), ICEI - 2022 Conference Proceedings, 2022.
- [3] G. Abraham, R. R. and M. Nithya, "Smart Agriculture Based on IoT and Machine Learning," 2021 5th International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC), Erode, India, 2021, pp. 414-419.

- [4] R. Reshma, V. Sathiyavathi, T. Sindhu, K. Selvakumar and L. SaiRamesh, "IoT based Classification Techniques for Soil Content Analysis and Crop Yield Prediction," 2020 Fourth International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud) (I-SMAC), Palladam, India, 2020, pp. 156-160.
- [5] A. M. Rajeswari, A. S. Anushiya, K. S. A. Fathima, S. S. Priya and N. Mathumithaa, "Fuzzy Decision Support System for Recommendation of Crop Cultivation based on Soil Type," 2020 4th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)(48184), Tirunelveli, India, 2020, pp. 768-773.
- [6] M. K. D P, A. A R, H. A R, M. G, K. M S and P. J, "Machine Learning – Based Crop Management: Towards Intelligent Recommendations for Crop, Fertilizer and Pesticide Optimization," 2023 International Conference on Recent Advances in Science and Engineering Technology (ICRASET), India, 2023, pp. 1-8.
- [7] G. B. P, R. S, D. U and S. K, "Crop Recommendation Systems using Machine Learning Algorithms," 2023 International Conference on Recent Advances in Science and Engineering Technology (ICRASET), India, 2023, pp. 1-5.
- [8] M. Raja. G., B. Deepa, Nijanthan, B. Swapna, B. S. Divya and P. J. Chate, "Internet of Things (IoT) Assisted Smart Agriculture Monitoring and Summarization System using NodeMCU and Efficient Sensor Unit," 2023 9th International Conference on Smart Structures and Systems (ICSSS), CHENNAI, India, 2023, pp. 1-6.
- [9] R. Singh and R. M. Bhavadharini, "An Investigation on Machine Learning Algorithms for Crop Yield Prediction," 2023 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN), India, 2023, pp. 1-6.
- [10] P. Kumar, H. Varun Prabhu and H. N. Champa, "Crop Recommendation using Ensemble Stacking Machine Learning approach," 2023 IEEE 3rd Mysore Sub Section International Conference (MysuruCon), HASSAN, India, 2023, pp. 1-6.
- [11] Kiran, P. B D, B. B S, S. Kumar D S and S. K V, "Machine Learning Models Based Crop Recommendation and Plant Disease Identification for Real Time Application," 2023 International Conference on Ambient Intelligence, Knowledge Informatics and Industrial Electronics (AIKIIE), Ballari, India, 2023, pp. 1-5.
- [12] P. Pawar, V. Shinde, A. Raut, S. Suke, K. Kolpe and A. Manna, "An Automated Combined System for Crop Prediction and Yield Prediction Using Deep Hybrid Learning Technique," 2023 7th International Conference On Computing, Communication, Control And Automation (ICCUBEA), Pune, India, 2023, pp. 1-5.
- [13] D. Timko, A. Elangovan, A. Elangovan, M. Sharko and A. Ahmadi, "A low-cost IoT-based Smart Farming System For Crop Recommendation and Resource Management," 2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData), Sorrento, Italy, 2023, pp. 3516-3523.
- [14] Y. N. Prajapati, S. Tomar, P. Singh, A. Gupta, V. Kumar and N. Arora, "A New Approach of Machine Learning And Deep Learning Algorithms Based Crop Yield Prediction," 2023 International Conference on Quantum Technologies, Communications, Computing, Hardware and Embedded Systems Security (iQ-CCHESS), KOTTAYAM, India, 2023, pp. 1-4.
- [15] G. Davrazos, T. Panagiotakopoulos, S. Kotsiantis and A. Kameas, "IoT-Enabled Crop Recommendation in Smart Agriculture Using Machine Learning," 2023 14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA), Volos, Greece, 2023, pp. 1-4.
- [16] P. Ayesha Barvin and T. Sampradeepraj "Crop Recommendation Systems Based on Soil and Environmental Factors Using Graph Convolution Neural Network: A Systematic Literature Review" 10th International Electronic Conference on Sensors and Applications (ECSA 2023).
- [17] Jangale Neha, Gawali Sayali, Tikole Snehal, Gandhale Pradnya, Prof. Sayyed J.I "Crop Recommendation System" International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education (IJARIIE 2023).
- [18] Ms. Sarika Gambhir, Manish Sharma, Khushboo Agarwal, Keshav Kumar, Lakshya Kumar, Mayank Chaudhary "Crop Recommendation System Using Machine Learning" International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET 2023).
- [19] Priyadharshini A, Swapneel Chakraborty, Aayush Kumar, Omen Rajendra Pooniwalla "Intelligent Crop Recommendation System using Machine Learning" 5th International Conference on Computing Methodologies and Communication (ICCMC 2021).
- [20] D.Jayanarayana Reddy, Dr M. Rudra Kumar "Crop Yield Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithm" 5th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS 2021).